

Empirical Research on the Impact of Foreign Direct Investment on Growth in Vietnam's Economy

Author's Details: (1) Ph.D scholar Minh Ngoc Ngo, College of Economics and Trade, Hunan University, China: **Corresponding author,** (2) Prof. Shujin Zhu, College of Economics and Trade, Hunan University, China.

Abstract: *By employing the difference Generalized Moment of Method (GMM) and the Pooled Mean Group (PMG) methods, the paper analyzes the role of foreign direct investment (FDI) and other factors in economic growth in Vietnam in the period 2000-2015. Besides, the paper clarifies the spillover effects of FDI to other variables in the model through Granger causality test. The research collects the most balance updated data from 43 provinces or cities to run regressions. For the first time, the recurrent expenditure variable is put into the model. The fact of encoding geography control variable instead of dummy one as previous studies is another novelty of the paper. The results indicate that FDI has a positive and significant impact on Vietnamese economic growth in the long-term. Moreover, it also affirms the two-way causal relationship between FDI and other independent variables as private investment, labor force, tax revenues, infrastructure, trade openness and technology gap. This will serve as a basis for mapping out policies over FDI to boost economic growth in the coming time.*

Key words: *Inward FDI, Economic growth, Panel data, Geography, Wealth, Vietnam.*

1. Problem statement

Vietnam implemented renovation process to open up an economy to the rest of the world since the year 1986. The first Law of Foreign Investment in Vietnam was dated 29th December 1987 and for the first time, the law established a regime under which FDI could enter into. By the end of 2015, there was approximately 130 billion United State dollar (USD) of disbursed FDI in Vietnam. Since then, FDI has positively contributed to socio-economic development in many ways. The average growth rate of Vietnamese economy is roughly 6.5 percent a year during period 2000-2015. This capital source helps increase gross domestic product (GDP) per capita remarkably, transforming Vietnam from one of the world's poorest to a lower middle-income country. To date, as global economy faces some difficulties, Vietnam continues to expand international trade to attract more FDI inflows. The fact raises the question that what is the relationship between FDI and economic growth which needs to be studied in more detail. Although some researchers have been done to solve the problem, however, the techniques, methods and data are not completed and updated. All schools of thought in economics emphasize on some factors driving growth as capital, labor force and technology. For developing countries where growth-drivers are limited, the role of FDI becomes more important in promoting economic growth because it helps address the gap between investment and domestic savings. Many domestic and foreign papers confirm that FDI has a positive effect on economic growth, international trade expansion, science and technology diffusion and others. Nonetheless, there is a few studies that do not detect the nexus between FDI and economic growth or even hinder domestic investment leading to negative impact on economic growth. In that context, it raises a question of does FDI inflow have an impact on Vietnam's economic growth as employing the most updated panel data? And what needs to be done to further leverage FDI in the coming years? This paper will attempt to explore the answers.

2. Literature review

There are many papers studying the relationship between FDI and economic growth rate. Some of the major papers are reviewed hereafter. Neo-classical economists develop models indicating the nexus between FDI and economic growth. Assuming that technical progress and labor force are exogenous variables and FDI affects positively on technology, Solow (1956) argues that it also positively contributes to economic growth. De Gregorio (1992), in his study on twelve Latin American in the period 1950-1985, discovers that FDI indeed has a positive impact on economic growth. This positive contribution is also found on a larger scale as Blomstrom

et al. (1994) conduct their study in 78 developing and 23 developed countries over the period 1960-1985. Later, in a research spanning, from 1970 to 1989 in 69 developing countries, Borensztein et al. (1998) discover that FDI not only has positive influence on economic growth but also contribute strongly to the development of human capital in the host country. The consistently positive role of FDI in economic growth is asserted once more in the study of Campos and Kinoshita (2002) upon examining 25 Central and Eastern European and former Soviet Union transition economies. More interestingly, Chowdhury and Marvrotas (2003) study the causal interplay between FDI and growth in the cases of Chile, Malaysia and Thailand during period 1969-2000. They discover that GDP leads to FDI for Chile while there is a bi-directional causality between the two in Malaysia and Thailand. The paper of Khawar (2005) confirms FDI's positive impacts on economic growth in an empirical cross-country study in the period 1970-1992. Yao (2006) arrives at the same conclusion in the case of China during 1978-2000. Similarly, Bhandari et al. (2007) show similar results in the case of East European countries. Most recently in 2014, Omri and Kahouli demonstrate that FDI positively affects economic growth in the Middle East and North Africa countries.

Regarding FDI, upon analyzing Vietnam's FDI statistics from 1988 to 2003, Mai (2003) finds that FDI has a positive effect on growth of the economy as a whole. Huong and Nhuong (2003) compare and analyze the movements of FDI inflows to Vietnam and China in the period 1979-2002 and draw some lessons for Vietnam. They verify the important role of FDI on Vietnam's development in terms of economic growth, structural change and job creation. Pham (2004) asserts that Vietnam's economic growth is largely dependent on foreign invested capital in the period 1988-2003. Then, Hoa (2004) concludes that FDI positively impacts on economic growth through the formation and accumulation of capital assets. In addition, there is evidence to support the relationship between FDI and human resource. Phuc (2004) argues that Vietnam's growth rate is largely dependent on foreign invested sector and demonstrates the considerable contribution of FDI to value added of industry sector, capital formulation, job creation and balance of payments. Anh et al. (2006) indicates how FDI influences capital formation and growth rate in Vietnam's economy. Lan (2006) confirms the positive role of FDI not only on economic growth but also on domestic investment. Anwar and Nguyen (2011) reaffirm the positive effect of FDI on Vietnam's economic growth over the period 1996-2005. Chien et al. (2012) also make the same conclusion in their study on researching the competition among some provinces to attract more FDI inflows. Moreover, Chien and Linh (2013) find out the two-way relationship between FDI and economic growth as investigating the causality.

In comparison with all the previous studies, the paper owns some novelties as hereafter. Firstly, the paper employs the most updated panel data (from 2000 to 2015). Secondly, this is the first time the econometric model puts the recurrent expenditure variable into. Thirdly, the paper applies encoding the geography control variable instead of using dummy variable as other past researches.

3. Research objective

The research attempts to evaluate the impact of FDI on growth rate in the both short-run and long-run in Vietnamese economy by employing the most updated panel data of 43 provinces or cities from 2000 to 2015. Furthermore, the paper investigates the relationship between FDI and other independent variables in the model. On the base of the research results, the paper suggests some policy implications to further leverage the positive impact of FDI in the coming years.

4. Methodology and empirical results

4.1 Variables and data description

Data of this research is the most updated panel one derived officially from General Statistical Office of Vietnam from 2000 to 2015. Descriptive statistics of the variables are reported in Table 2.

Table 1: Model's variables and interpretation

Variables	Label	Interpretation
Economic growth	GDP	Logarithm of real GDP per capita
Private investment	PRI	Logarithm of private investment
Foreign direct investment	FDI	Logarithm of disbursed FDI
Public investment	PUI	Public investment divided by real GDP
Labor	LF	Labor force divided by population
Tax revenue	TR	Tax revenue divided by real GDP
Recurrent expenditure	REXP	Recurrent expenditure divided by real GDP
Trade openness	OPEN	Total revenues of export and import divided by real GDP
Infrastructure	TELE	Logarithm of the number of fixed and cellphone post-paid
Consumer price index	CPI	Logarithm of consumer price index
Technology gap	GAP	(Local GDP - national GDP) divided by national GDP
Local characteristic	GEO	Based on the local classification
Local level of development	WEALTH	Based on the adjustment from local budget to state budget

The results of correlation between the variables in the empirical model point out that almost all pairs of variables had a statistically significant at 5% level. In particular, strong correlation pairs (TELE, PRI) and (TELE, GDP) indicate that private investment source is employed to modernize infrastructure aiming at promoting economic growth in recent years. All remaining pairs of other variables are normally valued, therefore, it is appropriate to put these variables into the model.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of the variables

Variables	Obs.	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max
GDP	670	1.333368	0.663153	0.155361	4.068367
PRI	670	6.74519	1.057916	3.727837	10.23986
FDI	670	4.533486	2.235128	-3.953663	9.107597
LF	670	52.13863	5.536087	35.78148	67.6647
PUI	670	19.76887	14.21516	2.705218	180.6794
TR	670	17.91242	13.25944	2.470407	73.08741
REXP	670	12.27711	7.092791	0.935609	55.59237
TELE	670	4.569904	1.224787	1.512046	7.822725
OPEN	670	76.69078	112.0303	.7018592	749.1873
CPI	670	4.680823	0.070015	4.50888	5.56145
GAP	670	-2.77474	118.8526	-65.34832	945.0399

Table 3: Correlation coefficients matrix

	GDP	PRI	FDI	LF	PUI	TR	REXP	TELE	OPEN	CPI	GAP
GDP	1										
PRI	0.62**	1									
FDI	0.65**	0.49**	1								
LF	0.08**	0.33**	0.10**	1							
PUI	-	-	-	-	1						
TR	0.22**	0.19**	0.15**	0.11**		1					
REXP	0.54**	0.30**	0.49**	-	0.06		1				
TELE	-	-	-	0.13**	0.33**	-		1			
OPEN	0.22**	0.11**	0.30**	0.30**	-0.05	0.41**	0.06**		1		
CPI	0.72**	0.82**	0.54**	0.30**	-	0.42**	-0.17**	0.40**		1	
GAP	0.45**	0.40**	0.54**	0.14**	-	0.16**					1
	0.28**	0.27**	0.15**	0.35**	0.01	0.07**	0.16**	0.38**	0.11**		
	0.73**	0.12**	0.40**	-	-	0.37**	-0.30**	0.23**	0.21**	-0.00	
				0.27**	0.20**						

Note: The asterisk ** denotes the statistical significance at the 5 percent level.

There are two methods which will be employed in handling panel data in this research. The paper employs STATA software to run the difference GMM of Arellano-Bond (1991) to assess the impact of FDI on economic growth. Subsequently, PMG method of Pesaran, Shin and Smith (1999) is investigated to evaluate the correction adjustment speed as well as the long-term co-integration of FDI in relation to economic growth. The two major regression methods are applied to exploit their own strengths and complement to each other, contributing to a more completed answers to research question. The paper will be implemented through the main following steps. Firstly, it tests the stationarity of all variables; secondly the Granger causality is examined to assess the spillover effects of FDI; thirdly the difference GMM regression is done; fourthly co-integration is tested by Westerlund test; lastly PMG regression is analyzed.

4.2 Model

The paper develops the empirical model based on the past literature. The model is presented in equation (1) to investigate the impact of FDI inflows and other factors on economic growth in Viet Nam:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Y_{it-1} + \beta_2 X_{it} + \beta_3 \text{CONTROL}_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

In which:

i is province or city, the paper collects the data of 43 provinces or cities out of 63 ones in Vietnam.

t is the time, from the year 2000 to 2015.

Y is economic growth, derived from real GDP per capita of the province or city. This variable's unit is measured in million domestic currency at the based-year 2000. The first-order difference of Y approximately equals to the growth rate. With equation (1), converting the Y_{it-1} variable to the left-hand side the paper obtains the first-degree difference of Y . Most empirical studies on the impact of FDI on economic growth applies this variable as a proxy for economic growth (Adeolu, 2007; Wu Jyun-Yi and Hsu Chih-Chiang, 2008. Elboiashi Hosein Ali, 2011).

X_{it} is a set of variables in the Cobb-Douglas model, while FDI is measured in million USD then private investment is measured in billion domestic currency at the based-year 2000 and labor force is represented by a number of people.

$CONTROL_{it}$ is a set of control variables, including:

(i) Some fiscal variables (tax revenues, public investment and recurrent expenditure)

To a certain extent, tax policy has the effect of stimulating economic growth. In contrast, tax collection can also slow down growth. The higher the tax rate, the more distorted the economy. Moreover, according to the theory of taxation, the changes of levying tax will make economic identities adjust their behaviors and create deadweight loss. The paper considers this variable in order to assess the tax distortion in economic growth and test the consistency of the model.

Public investment source plays an important role in economic growth. Not only that, it also does crucial role in directing other investment resources, especially in low efficiency areas and socio-performance fields. This is the main reason leading to the fact that public investment may not promote positive growth but sometimes against growth, especially in developing economies.

The composition of the recurrent expenditures varies widely, namely administrative expenses, maintenance, regular expenditures on education, science, technology and so on. Bose et al. (2007) argues that education, science, technology, environment and health care are the keys to future economic prosperity. Previous studies on FDI and economic growth, recurrent expenditure factor has not been employed in the empirical model.

(ii) Variables reflect local characteristics (geography, wealth of the locality)

The paper bases on urban and economic features to derive the geographical characteristics of the locality. Accordingly, based on government regulations, there are some types of locality as special type, city directly under central-government, provinces in the key economic zone and other cases. With its geographic characteristics, it helps to exploit the regional dimension of FDI inflows for economic growth.

The paper employs the rate of revenue distribution to the central budget as a proxy for measuring the level of development and the wealth of the locality. This control variable helps to exploit the regional features of FDI inflows and the wealth of the locality in relation to economic growth.

(iii) Other control variables (infrastructure, trade openness, consumer price index, and technology gap)

The paper applies the number of post-paid mobile and fixed-line subscribers to derive as a proxy for infrastructure.

Based on some other empirical researches, the paper investigates total import-export turnover as a proxy for trade openness.

The impacts of the consumer price index on economic growth may be negative or positive ways. Positive impact exits the potential benefits of the consumer price index to improve savings and investment. Negative impact may be caused by increasing the transaction costs of business activities.

The technology gap measures the variation in local development relative to the national average. The technology gap is measured by the ratio of the per capita income of the United States (technology leader) to the GDP per capita of the recipient country in the study of FDI efficiency and growth in developing countries (Elboiashi, Hosein Ali, 2011).

From the above analysis, based on the theory and results of the past empirical studies on the impact of FDI on economic growth, the paper determines the expected marks of the variables in the model as following:

Table 4: Expected marks of the variables

Criteria	Variables	Expected marks
Variables in Cobb-Douglas function	PRI	+
	FDI	+
	LF	+
Fiscal variables	TR	+/-
	PUI	+/-
	REXP	+/-
Control variables	TELE	+
	OPEN	+
	CPI	+/-
	GAP	+
Local variables	GEO	+
	WEALTH	+

4.3 Unit root tests

Table 5: Unit root tests

Variable	Augmented Dickey Fuller		Phillips – Perron	
	No trend	With trend	No trend	With trend
GDP	1.0000	0.8620	1.0000	0.1276
PRI	0.2373	0.0000***	0.5054	0.0000***
FDI	0.3361	0.0000***	0.0002***	0.0000***
LF	0.9314	0.0001***	1.0000	0.0000***
PUI	0.0018**	0.0190**	0.0111**	0.0549*
TR	0.3450	0.0004***	0.0005***	0.0216**
REXP	0.0000***	0.0000***	0.0000***	0.0000***
TELE	0.0093***	1.0000	0.0000***	1.0000
OPEN	0.0000***	0.0000***	0.0000***	0.0069***
CPI	1.0000	0.9978	0.0000***	0.0000***
GAP	0.9999	0.9267	1.0000	0.9932

Note: The asterisks ** and *** denote the statistical significance at the 5 and 1 percent levels, respectively.

The paper applies Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) tests to verify the stationarity of the panel data with and without trend and lag 2. The results are reported in table 5. As demonstrated, almost all variables are stationary in level form except GDP and GAP variables. Thus, the paper continues to test the stationarity of the first difference of the two variables above. The results of these first differences are integrated of order one with trend by ADF test at a 1% significance level (Δ GDP= 0.2661; Δ GAP= 0.8465).

4.4 Granger causality

As theoretically mentioned, FDI affects economic growth on both horizontal and vertical axis. Based on the empirical model of economic growth, the paper examines the Granger causality between FDI and economic growth-derived variables to assess the spillover effects of FDI inflows. The main objective of the Granger causality is to determine the horizontal and vertical spillover effect between FDI and other factors as private investment, labor force, tax revenues, infrastructure, trade openness and technology gap. The paper investigates in more restricted way when adding lag (1) and lag (2) of each independent variable. The relationship among

variables is established through the statistically significant level of the Wald test and the partial meanings of the regression coefficients.

The results in table 6 affirm the two-way causal relationship between FDI and private investment, labor force, tax revenues, infrastructure, trade openness and technology gap. This helps the paper arrives at conclusion that FDI inflows have a spillover effect on the factors that drive economic growth through the impact on private investment, the increase in human capital, the generation of revenues for the state budget, the stimulation of infrastructure development and the expansion of trade openness.

Table 6: Granger causality

Dependent variable	Independent variable	Lag (0)	Lag (-1)	Lag (-2)	Cons.	Wald test
FDI	PRI	0.294138	0.289694	0.411907**	-210.136***	0.0000***
PRI	FDI	0.174868***	0.065360***	0.072092**	547.132***	0.0000***
FDI	LF	11.36365***	3.519572	3.564486	-503.598***	0.0000***
LF	FDI	0.010971***	0.004749***	0.004711***	43.4384***	0.0000***
FDI	TR	0.009082***	0.004472	-0.002188	13.2608***	0.0000***
TR	FDI	11.36362***	3.519576	3.564486	-503.595***	0.0001***
FDI	TELE	-0.007201	0.083760	0.724610***	105.482***	0.0000***
TELE	FDI	0.277193***	0.105524***	0.063212**	277.556***	0.0000***
FDI	OPEN	0.348995***	0.069268	0.276811**	406.531***	0.0000***
OPEN	FDI	0.087995***	0.043639	0.050485**	2.195525	0.0000***
FDI	GAP	0.344568	0.091596	0.499991**	463.125***	0.0000***
GAP	FDI	0.028279**	0.014101	0.004359	-22.0076***	0.0009***

Note: The asterisks ** and *** denote the statistical significance at the 5 and 1 percent levels, respectively.

The paper realizes from the fact that FDI tends to focus on the localities owning more favorable conditions on the geography and modernized level such as Hanoi capital or Ho Chi Minh city. Therefore, the paper will add some instrument variables to test the characteristics of FDI inflows into Vietnam in more detailed. These instrument variables are following:

WEALTH: this variable measures the prosperity of each province or city. The paper relies on the ratio of regulating from local revenues to the central budget to derive the wealth of the localities. Specifically, the rate of local revenue regulation on central budget over 60% will be encoded as 4; from 50% to 60% as 3; from 10% to 50% as 2; up to 10% as 1 and the rest of encoding 0.

GEO: this variable reflects local geographic features. In fact, some previous studies measure this variable by dummy one. However, by the difference GMM method, the regression results will be biased because it will be eliminated when differentiating dummy variable. Hence, the paper bases on the urban characteristics of the provinces in Vietnam to make classification. Concretely, some special urban cities will be encoded as 4, cities directly under central government are 3, key economic provinces are 2 and the remaining one is 1.

Δ FDI: this variable measures the difference of local FDI in comparison with the national average. Δ FDI reveals how local FDI is compared to the national average. From localized measurement variables, it helps to exploit more in depth the nexus between FDI inflows and economic growth rate. For that reason, the paper integrates some integrated variables such as (WEALTH* Δ FDI) and (WEALTH*GEO* Δ FDI) to put into empirical model.

WEALTH* Δ FDI: this variable reflects the FDI inflow which is attracted by the prosperity of each locality.

WEALTH*GEO* Δ FDI: this variable reflects the FDI inflow which is attracted by both the prosperity and the modernized level of each locality.

Table 7: Descriptive statistics of the instrument variables

Variables	Obs.	Mean	Std.dev.	Minimum	Maximum
Δ FDI	670	111.8934	727.5523	-274.3815	6272.153
GEO	670	1.586567	0.807735	1	4
WEALTH	670	0.514925	1.093089	0	4
WEALTH* Δ FDI	670	191.6339	720.7636	-208.5566	6272.153
WEALTH*GEO* Δ FDI	670	641.4339	2695.194	-417.1131	25088.61

In addition, the lag of the dependent variable, economic growth, is also taken into account in order to see how the relationship between growth rate this year affects growth rate in the following year. Based on the suggestion of Christophe Hurlin (2004), the paper applies lag (2). Accordingly, the optimal lag is expressed by the equation: $2 * K + 5 < T$; where: K is the lag, T is the time. According to the data $T = 16$, therefore, the optimal lags of less than 5 is reasonable.

4.5 Regression results

Table 8 presents regression results employing the difference GMM method. In order to assess the robustness of the empirical model, the paper runs initial regression for nine variables (private investment, FDI, labor force, public investment, tax revenue, recurrent expenditure, infrastructure, consumer price index, technology gap) and economic growth in lag 1 and 2. Then the paper continues to add the trade open variable in model 2, adding the (WEALTH* Δ FDI) variable in model 3 and consecutively adding the (WEALTH*GEO* Δ FDI) in model 4.

Some conclusions could be drawn from the regression results by the difference GMM method are: firstly, some endogenous variables are FDI, public investment, tax revenues (done in GMM), all the remaining variables are exogenous ones as economic growth, private investment, labor force, recurrent expenditures, infrastructure, trade openness, consumer price indexes, technology gaps, (WEALTH* Δ FDI), (WEALTH*GEO* Δ FDI) (done in instrument variable); secondly, the second-order Arellano-Bond test, AR (2), affirms that there have no auto-correlation in the model; thirdly, Sargan test asserts that the instrument variables used in the difference GMM are exogenous, meaning that these are not correlated with the residuals in the model; fourthly, on the partial impact of each independent variable on the dependent variable (economic growth), specifically, the private investment variables is statistically significant at 1% level; some others such FDI, labor force, public investment, trade openness is statistically significant at 5% level; some others such as infrastructure, recurrent expenditures, (WEALTH*GEO* Δ FDI) is statistically significant at 10% level and all the remaining variables like tax revenue, consumer price index, technology gap, (WEALTH* Δ FDI) are not statistically significant. Moreover, all four models yielded almost a single result which confirms the robustness of the model and the consistency when adding observed variables.

Table 8: Regression results by the difference GMM

Variables	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3		Model 4	
	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.
GDP (-1)	0.276672	0.000***	0.267411	0.001***	0.267966	0.001***	0.224995	0.005***
GDP (-2)	0.108271	0.078*	0.107281	0.084*	0.104867	0.096*	0.14128	0.024**
PRI	0.277935	0.000** *	0.275041	0.000***	0.280596	0.000***	0.276742	0.000***
FDI	0.027222	0.023**	0.032832	0.010***	0.031936	0.012**	0.025438	0.040**
LF	0.464527	0.071*	0.460252	0.075*	0.454268	0.084*	0.507525	0.042**
PUI	-0.219705	0.015**	-0.202952	0.026**	-0.205599	0.026**	-0.182394	0.038**
TR	-	0.171	-0.132760	0.145	-0.137430	0.137	-0.081209	0.377
	0.121137							
REXP	0.289699	0.089*	0.277789	0.106	0.265610	0.132	0.249971	0.138
TELE	0.032244	0.081*	0.029212	0.119	0.028153	0.140	0.031114	0.086*
OPEN			0.019718	0.040**	0.019703	0.043**	0.021342	0.023**
CPI	-0.134004	0.187	-0.123605	0.226	-0.125607	0.226	-0.108705	0.273
GAP	-0.001934	0.956	-0.008707	0.808	-0.008202	0.821	0.029223	0.424
WEALTH					0.002623	0.634	-0.021118	0.102
*ΔFDI								
WEALTH							0.006763	0.072*
*GEO*ΔFDI								
Obs.	541		541		541		541	
Sargan test	0.245		0.209		0.251		0.167	
AR(2)	0.320		0.372		0.369		0.473	

Note: The asterisks *, ** and *** denote the statistical significance at the 10, 5 and 1 percent levels, respectively.

4.6 Co-integration test and long-term regression

4.6.1 Co-integration test

By PMG regression, the paper deals with to estimate the dynamics of FDI to economic growth in the long-term on the basis of expanding private investment, labor force, public investment and tax revenues variables. Firstly, the paper conducts co-integration test of these variables. Westerlund (2007) has developed four criteria tests for panel data. The main idea is to test the co-integration by determining whether the corrected error exists or not. Considering the following error correction model:

$$\Delta y_{it} = \varphi_i + \alpha_{i1} \Delta y_{it-1} + \alpha_{i2} \Delta y_{it-2} + \dots + \alpha_{ip} \Delta y_{it-p} + \beta_{i0} \Delta x_{it} + \beta_{i1} \Delta x_{it-1} + \dots + \beta_{ip} \Delta x_{it-p} + \alpha_i y_{it-1} - \beta_i x_{it-1} + u_{it} \quad (2)$$

Statistical hypothesis for each unit as well as all panel data are null hypothesis (H_N): α_i=0 (∀i) against the alternative hypothesis (H_A): α_i<0 (∃i). α_i is the estimator of the error correction adjustment that reaches to the long-term equilibrium; -β_i/α_i x_{it} for all i sequences. G_α and G_t statistics test the statistically significant in the case of each table unit while the P_α and P_t statistics verify the statistical significance for the whole panel data. The rejection of the null hypothesis should be viewed as rejecting the co-integration of the entire panel data. The results of the co-integration test in Table 9 indicate that private investment, FDI, labor force, public investment and tax revenues are co-integrated with economic growth.

Table 9: Co-integration test

Dependent variable: GDP				
Independent variables	Gt	G α	Pt	P α
PRI	0.000***	0.000***	0.024**	0.000***
FDI	0.049**	0.000***	0.000***	0.000***
LF	0.000***	0.000***	0.000***	0.000***
PUI	0.000***	0.000***	0.042**	0.000***
TR	0.000***	0.000***	0.000***	0.000***

Note: The asterisks ** and *** denote the statistical significance at the 5 and 1 percent levels, respectively.

4.6.2 Long-term regression by PMG method

Table 10: Regression results by PMG method

Dependent variable: GDP			
Panel A: Long-run coefficients			
Independent variables	Coeff.	Std.	Prob.
PRI	0.857587	0.034145	0.000***
FDI	0.226173	0.011145	0.000***
LF	1.979529	0.477757	0.000***
PUI	-0.995545	0.104357	0.000***
TR	1.281256	0.195886	0.000***
Panel B: Short-run coefficients			
Correction coefficient	0.077029	0.036995	0.037**
Δ PRI	0.044149	0.021542	0.040**
Δ FDI	0.002794	0.005917	0.637
Δ LF	0.585168	0.418312	0.162
Δ PUI	-0.371592	0.230121	0.106
Δ TR	0.026417	0.101778	0.795
TELE	0.053632	0.015539	0.001***
OPEN	-0.180654	0.102723	0.079*
Cons.	33.05121	16.90499	0.051*
Observations		627	
Log Likelihood		-1455.111	

Note: The asterisks *, ** and *** denote the statistical significance at the 10, 5 and 1 percent levels, respectively.

Next, the paper runs the PMG regression and results are presented in Table 10. In the long-run, the impacts of all variables are statistically significant at a 1% level. In the short run, private investment, infrastructure and trade openness have a statistically significant impact on economic growth. Simultaneously, the correction coefficient is positive and statistically significant at 5% level. This means the speed of adjustment is low (0.07) when there has a shock making economic growth slip from the long-run equilibrium.

5. The main findings

By the difference GMM regression, the results show that the effect of FDI on economic growth is significant and consistent for all four models which demonstrate the model's robustness. Concretely, model 1 (with independent variables as FDI, private investment, labor force, public investment, tax revenue, recurrent expenditure, infrastructure, consumer price index, economic growth at lags 1 and 2) shows that the positive impact of FDI inflows on economic growth is significant at 5% level. In model 2 (adding the trade openness

variable into model 1), the partial impact of FDI on economic growth remains the same with a significance level of 1%. In model 3 (adding the integrated variable of $WEALTH*\Delta FDI$), the impact of FDI on economic growth is almost unchanged with a significance level of 5%. In model 4 (adding the integrated variable of $WEALTH*\Delta FDI*GEO$), it continues to indicate the positive effect of FDI on economic growth with a significance at 5% level. The regression results demonstrate the consistency and robustness of the model for assessing the effect of FDI inflows on economic growth in Vietnam.

Testing the long-term dynamics by PMG method, the results figure out the positive effect of FDI inflows on economic growth significantly at 1% level. Therefore, Vietnam should have priorities to exploit this source of capital to continue serving economic growth as well as to take full advantage of spillover effects. However, FDI inflows have no impacts on growth rate in the short-term. This reflects partly the instability of FDI's effect on growth rate in Vietnam's economy.

FDI inflows come into Vietnam is different from one province to another. This suggests a quantitative study to evaluate the impact of FDI inflows on Vietnam in order to provide a basis for policy-makers. By the difference GMM regression, it would be affirmed that the contribution of FDI inflows to economic growth is evident in those localities with high levels of development and modern infrastructure at 10% significance level (see table 8, model 4).

The empirical results confirm that private investment has significantly positive effects on both short-term and long-term growth which is achieved in both the difference GMM and PMG regressions. According to the difference GMM method, private investment has a strong impact on economic growth in all four models with a significance at 1% level. The results demonstrate the apparent effectiveness of private resources in growth rate. By PMG regression, private investment positively affects economic growth at a 5% significance level in the short-term and with a 1% significance level in the long-term.

The results indicate that labor force has a positively significant effect on economic growth. It also reveals the robustness of the model as adding some variables. The changes of the impacts are negligible with a significance level of 10% (for models 1, 2, 3) and a significance level of 5% (for model 4). Moreover, the results achieved by PMG regression also demonstrate the convergence of the impact of labor force on growth in the long-term with a significance at 1% level.

The results of the PMG regression proclaim that tax revenue is positively correlated with economic growth at a 1% significance level. This proves that appropriate of taxation revenue will stimulate growth rate. However, by the difference GMM regression, the results is insignificant statistically, which suggests that the impact of tax revenue on growth rate is unsustainable.

As can be seen from table 8, the public investment negatively impacts on economic growth. This is not as expected mark with both regression methods. According to the difference GMM method, the negative impact of public investment on economic growth is lowest at 0.18% (model 4) and the strongest negative impact is 0.21% (model 1) with the same level of significance at 5%. The PMG method shows that 1% increase in public investment will lead to decrease 0.99% in economic growth in the long-term with the significance level at 1%. These prove that the inefficiency of public investment source in Vietnam in the timeframe work.

The regression results by the difference GMM method show that recurrent expenditure has effects on economic growth in the same direction with a 10% significance level in model 1. However, the robustness of the model was not recorded when the outcomes of the difference GMM regressions for 2, 3, 4 models were statistically insignificant. This is in line with reality because the impact of recurrent expenditure on economic growth depends on its structure.

By the difference GMM regression, it would be asserted that the positive impact of infrastructure on economic growth with 10% significance level in both model 1 and model 4. As other developing economies, Vietnam's infrastructure is still weak so far, therefore, the role of infrastructure improvement is very significant to

economic growth. However, the robustness of the model is not guaranteed when this variable is not statistically significant in the models 2 and 3. That ascertains the positive impact of infrastructure on Vietnam's economic growth is inconsistent. This is also in line with the fact because its impact depends on specific period of time and mostly suitable for the conditions of the developing country.

The regression outcome by the difference GMM show that trade openness positively impacts on economic growth at a 5% significance level. In addition, the model was characterized by the consistency and the tightness when adding some other variables into the model 1. The result reveals that the trade openness plays important role in speeding up growth rate in the case of Vietnam. The results of the study are in line with the reality when the Vietnamese economy has made remarkable progress since opening up the economy in the year of 1986.

To sum up, the paper evaluates the impacts of FDI and some other variables affecting economic growth in the context of employing the most updated panel data and applying both the difference GMM and PMG methods. The results indicate that the model is statistically significant. By the standpoint of FDI, it has a significant impact on economic growth rate while the robustness of the model is also confirmed. Besides, private investment, labor force, trade openness, recurrent expenditure, and infrastructure also have a significant impact on Vietnam's economic growth. The paper also indicates the inefficiency of public investment, negatively affecting growth rate. The empirical research results are reliable basis to suggest policy implication in the coming time.

6. Conclusion and policy implication

The results of the difference GMM and PMG regressions indicate that FDI inflows as some other variables are important for economic growth in Vietnam. Therefore, some policy implications would be drawn from empirical research as following:

Firstly, it is necessary to further attract this source of capital by influencing the factors which help attract more FDI inflows such as (i) increase market size; (ii) push up the quantity of labor force; (iii) map out appropriate and stable macroeconomic policies; (iv) expand international trade. In addition, some solutions need to be built to exploit local characteristics to enhance the positive impact of FDI on Vietnam's economic growth. In which special attentions should be paid to exploiting the role of two special cities namely Hanoi capital and Ho Chi Minh city. Secondly, some other cities like Hai Phong, Da Nang and Can Tho are subsequent to attract and exploit FDI inflows for economic growth because of their good conditions. These localities will create a positive spillover effect to the whole region. The results show that the level of development and dynamism of the locality is a good catalyst for FDI inflows that contribute positively to economic growth. Simultaneously, it is necessary to select investors and specific projects so that FDI inflows bring about positive effects as soon as its disbursement, minimizing the negative impacts as well as other related issues as transfer pricing, environmental damage, money laundering, exhausted exploitation of natural resources, exploitation of cheap labor and unhealthy competition.

Secondly, it is necessary to exploit private investment to promote economic growth, especially in the conditions of limited and inefficient of public investment. Therefore, the role of private investment becomes more important in that context. To this end, it is necessary to improve legal framework in the direction of stimulating private investment resources, demonstrating the determination of central and local authorities to exploit this source of capital for economic development.

Thirdly, labor force also plays a crucial role in economic development. As such, it is necessary to pay enough attention to educate and train in terms of both quantity and quality aspects. The results show a significant positive impact of this factor on growth rate. Therefore, the investment in labor force should be detailed in the following directions, one hand, a part meets the practical requirement, the others undertake academic research and innovation to ensure immediate and long-term tasks to economic development.

Fourthly, research results show that tax revenues have a positive impact on economic growth. Therefore, the state budget operation must ensure not only the balance but also pay attention to stimulate economic growth. The use of state budget must be more positive than the negative effects caused by tax distortion on growth rate. The adjustment of tax distortion is very essential to ensure the dual objective of both budget balance and economic growth.

Fifthly, empirical results indicate that public investment negatively impacts on economic growth. The ineffectiveness of public investment will lead to other negative consequences such as pressing on domestic inflation and making macroeconomic imbalances. In reality, public investment in Vietnam is allocated across almost all sectors in the economy. Therefore, the fact of public reinvestment is urgent and vital tasks for the Vietnamese government. Only by doing so could the Vietnamese economy ensure to achieve sustainable growth rate in the long-term.

Next, Vietnam's infrastructure in reality is still in the process of development. Even so, its impact on growth is positive. In developing economies, infrastructure is the driving force and catalyst for growth. Despite the size of the economy is not large, Vietnam is still one of the countries in Asia which strongly invest in infrastructure development. Therefore, in the coming time, this tendency needs to be maintained so as to create advantages in attracting more FDI to promote economic growth.

Lastly, trade openness has a significant impact on economic growth, which is evident since Vietnam moves to market economy since 1986. The change of an economy is expressed in various perspectives, from growth rate to people's income. Thus, in future, it is necessary to continue to focus on promoting export activities in order to push up its contribution to economic growth. Concurrently, the central government also needs to minimize the adverse effects which trade openness would bring about to the economy.

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